

Studies on Some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Copper(II) with 8-Hydroxyquinoline and Salicylic Acids. Relation between Stability Constants and Antimicrobial Activity[†]

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Manuscript received 10 May 1984, accepted 29 April 1985

A series of mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} with the general formula Cu(OX)(L), where HOX = 8-hydroxyquinoline; L = salicylic, 5-chloro, 3,5-dibromo, 3,5-diiodo, 3,5-dinitro and thio salicylic acids, have been isolated in pure state and their antimicrobial activity against various bacteria and fungi is examined critically. The formation constant of these complexes are determined potentiometrically using Irving-Rossotti technique. The difference in their toxic action against various bacteria and fungi has been explained on the basis of their formation constant and liposolubility. The molecular bonding parameters, namely the σ bond and the in-plane π bond coefficients α^1 and β^2 , respectively derived from epr data of these complexes support the observed formation constants.

8-Hydroxyquinoline (oxine), salicylic acid and their derivatives have long been established as potential antimicrobial agents and drugs^{1,2}. The role of mixed ligand complexes in biological process has been well recognised³. The stabilities of mixed chelates are of great importance in biological systems as many metabolic and toxicological functions are dependent upon stability. Many attempts have been made to correlate the stability of the metal-ligand complexes with their antimicrobial activity⁴⁻⁸.

Martell⁹ studied the mixed ligand complexes of the type where two ligands form complex with the metal in wide pH range, and the first ligand-metal complex does not get dissociated even at higher pH. In the present paper, an attempt has been made to apply Irving-Rossotti method¹⁰ to study the formation constant of the mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} with 8-hydroxyquinoline (HOX) and various salicylic acids (H₂A), viz. salicylic, 5-chloro, 3,5-dibromo, 3,5-diiodo, 3,5-dinitro and thio salicylic acids, which are of the type studied by Martell. The formation constants thus obtained are critically compared with their antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

Material and Measurements: All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. In order to avoid the complexing tendency of the anion, Cu(ClO₄)₂ was prepared and the metal content determined by EDTA titration. All the solutions were prepared in conductivity water.

A Systronics 335 digital pH meter with a Toshniwal-Moellor glass electrode (accuracy ± 0.01 pH unit)

was used for all the pH measurements and calibrated by buffers of pH 4.00 and 9.20 (30°). The titrations were carried out at 30° ($\pm 1^\circ$) in a constant temperature bath. The ionic strength of the solutions was maintained constant at 0.05 M by the addition of appropriate amount of 0.5 M sodium perchlorate solution. Due to low solubility of the chelates in water, 75% ethanol was employed as the solvent.

Since the reading given by pH meter is true hydrogen activity when the solvent is water, to get correct hydrogen ion concentration calibration of the glass electrode was done as described earlier^{11,12}. To accomplish this, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1.00 and 1.50 ml of 0.001058 M perchloric acid were added separately to 35 ml of pure ethanol in 50 ml volumetric flask maintaining the ionic strength at 0.05 M and then the total volume made upto the mark with double-distilled water. After thorough equilibration, the pH meter reading (B) of the solution were measured. The B values so obtained from the calibration solution are related to the true hydrogen concentration in the medium studied by equation (1).

$$U_H = \text{antilog}(-B)/[H^+] \quad (1)$$

where, [H⁺] is the stoichiometric hydrogen ion concentration used. By correcting the concentration to activity, the equation becomes

$$-\log [H^+] = B + \log U_H^0 + \log \gamma_{\pm}$$

where, $U_H^0 = U_H/\gamma_{\pm}$, and γ is the mean activity coefficient of hydrogen ion in the present medium (0.92), which is comparable with the reported data¹³.

The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen-free nitrogen gas

[†] Abstracted in the Proceedings of 29th International Congress of Pure and Applied Chemistry held at Cologne, West Germany, June 1988.

through an assembly containing the electrodes to keep out carbon dioxide.

Ionisation constant of ligands and stability constant of complexes: In all the experimental determination of ionisation constants of the ligands and stability constants of the complexes, the following solutions (i-viii) were prepared and titrated against carbonate-free NaOH solution (0.1123 M) following Irving-Rossotti technique.

(i) 0.001058 M HClO₄ — A, (ii) A+0.001 M oxine — B, (iii) B+0.00098 M Cu^{II} — C, (iv) C+0.001 M salicylic/substituted salicylic acid — D, (v) A+0.001 M salicylic/substituted salicylic acid — E, (vi) E+0.00098 M Cu^{II} — F, (vii) A+0.005 M oxine/salicylic/substituted salicylic acid—G, (viii) G+0.00098 M Cu^{II}. The plots of pH against volume of alkali have been presented in case of Cu^{II}-8-hydroxyquinoline-salicylic acid (Fig. 1) and Cu^{II}-8-hydroxyquinoline-3,5-diiodosalicylic acid (Fig. 2) systems. The nature of the curves of other substituted salicylic acids follow the same pattern as that of the salicylic acid system.

The experimental details regarding the preparation of the complexes and their physicochemical data are given in our earlier communication¹¹.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand stability constant: Salicylic acid and its substituted derivatives may be considered

Fig. 1. pH titration curve, Cu(OX)(HSA) system : (A) HClO₄, (B) (HOX), (C) Cu(OX) 1 : 1, (D) (H₂SA), (E) Cu(HSA) 1 : 1, and (F) Cu(OX)(HSA) 1 : 1 : 1.

Fig 2. pH titration curve, Cu(OX)(2I-HSA) system : (A) HClO₄, (B) (HOX), (C) Cu(OX) 1 : 1, (D) (2I-H₂SA), (E) Cu(2I-HSA) 1 : 1, and (F) Cu(OX)(2I-HSA) 1 : 1 : 1.

as dibasic acids having two dissociable H⁺ ions for COOH and OH groups and can therefore be represented as H₂A, while oxine with one dissociable hydrogen can be represented as HOX. However, the oxine with its heterocyclic nitrogen atom undergoes protonation below pH 5, and as the complex formation is studied from pH 2.5, pK_{NH} of the oxine is also determined for calculating the free ligand concentration.

The proton-ligand formation number $\bar{n}_A$ is given by equation (2)

$$\bar{n}_A = Y - \frac{(V_2 - V_1)(N + E^0)}{(V^0 + V_1) T_1^0} \quad (2)$$

where Y = displaceable hydrogen atoms, 2 for the salicylic acids and 1 for 8-hydroxyquinoline. E⁰ and T₁⁰ are the initial concentrations of the mineral acid and the reagent, respectively. V₁ and V₂ are the volumes of alkali of normality N required for the acid and the reagent titrations, respectively at a given pH, and V⁰ is the initial volume of the solution which is 100 ml in each case.

Formation curves are obtained by plotting values of $\bar{n}_A$ vs pH of the system. Values of pK₁ and pK₂

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS* OF Cu^{II} WITH 8-HYDROXYQUINOLINE AND VARIOUS SALICYLIC ACIDS
 $\text{I}=0.05, \text{NaClO}_4$; Temp. 30°

Sl. no.	Ligand	pK_1	pK_2	$\log K_{\text{CuSA}}^{\text{Cu}}$	$\log K_{\text{CuSA}_2}^{\text{CuSA}}$	$\log K_{\text{CuOXSA}}^{\text{CuOX}}$
				X	Y	
1.	8-Hydroxyquinoline	4.31	11.30	12.01	10.98	—
		3.97 ^a	11.48	12.38	11.42 ^b	
2.	Salicylic acid	3.30	13.25	9.97	7.66	9.61
		2.97 ^c	13.59 ^c	10.52	8.66 ^d	
		2.81 ^e		10.60 ^f	7.85 ^f	
		2.85 ^g	13.60 ^g			
		2.32	13.24	10.45	8.61 ^h	
		3.12	13.30 ⁱ			
3.	5-Chlorosalicylic acid	2.71	13.22	9.61	7.34	9.21
		2.43 ^h	12.5 ^h	10.05 ^h	7.54 ^h	
		2.71 ^k	12.22 ^k	9.66 ^k		
		2.69	12.22 ^a			
4.	3,5-Dibromosalicylic acid	2.55	10.43	9.30	7.30	8.20
		2.55	10.43 ^a			
5.	3,5-Diodosalicylic acid	3.81	11.20	8.91	7.19	8.45
6.	3,5-Dinitrosalicylic acid	1.56	7.68	6.60	4.89	7.00
		1.31 ^l	7.00 ^l	6.70	4.95 ^l	
7.	Thiosalicylic acid	5.40	9.50	9.10	7.21	8.71
		5.44 ^m	9.52 ⁿ			

X for $\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{HOX} \rightleftharpoons \text{CuOX}^+ + \text{H}^+$

Y for $\text{Cu}^{2+} + 2\text{HOX} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}(\text{OX})_2 + 2\text{H}^+$

^aRef. 12. ^bRef. 13. ^cRef. 14. ^dRef. 15. ^eRef. 16. ^fRef. 17. ^gRef. 18. ^hRef. 19. ⁱRef. 20. ^jRef. 21. ^kRef. 22.
^lRef. 23. ^mRef. 24. ⁿRef. 25.

* The accuracy of values are ± 0.1 pH unit.

are estimated by noting the pH at which $\bar{n}_A = 1.5$ and 0.5, respectively. The accurate values are determined by pointwise calculations using equations (3) and (4).

$$\log \frac{(\bar{n}_A - 1)}{(2 - \bar{n}_A)} = pK_1 \quad (pH \text{ in the range } 1 < \bar{n}_A < 2) \quad (3)$$

$$\log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{(1 - \bar{n}_A)} = pK_2 \quad (pH \text{ in the range } \bar{n}_A < 1) \quad (4)$$

The average of the values obtained by solving the linear equations are given along with the values reported in the literature, as available, in Table 1.

Metal-ligand stability constant: The complex formation between Cu^{II} and different substituted salicylic acids and oxine (Fig. 1) is indicated by (i) the significant departure, starting at pH 2.8 of the metal complex titration curve, from the reagent curve and (ii) the change in colour from light green to dark green. The equilibria involved in Cu^{II} -salicylic acid or substituted salicylic acids and Cu^{II} -8-hydroxyquinoline system can be given as

However, in solid complexes it is assumed that the phenolic proton of salicylic acid is again attached

for neutralising the complex before separation as a solid.

$\bar{n}$ (metal-ligand formation number) is obtained by using the expression

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(V_2 - V_3)[(N+E) + T_M^0(Y - \bar{n}_A)]}{(V^0 + V_2) T_M^0 \bar{n}_A}$$

where, V_3 and V_2 are the volumes of alkali required for the metal complex and the reagent titrations, respectively at a given pH, and T_M^0 is the initial concentration of Cu^{II} . The remaining quantities have the same significance as given in equation (2).

In using the method of Irving and Rossotti for calculating $\bar{n}$, the portion of metal complex curve where $(V_3 - V_2)$ is not too small, is used to achieve greater accuracy. Values of $pL = -\log [L]$ where $[L]$ is the free ligand concentrations, are calculated by equation (5).

$$pL = \log \frac{1 + ([\text{H}^+]/K_1) + ([\text{H}^+]^2/K_1 K_2)}{T_M^0 - \bar{n} T_M^0} \times \frac{V^0 + V_2}{V^0} \quad (5)$$

From a knowledge of $\bar{n}$ and pL values, formation curves for copper complexes are constructed.

$\log K_{\text{CuSA}}^{\text{Cu}}$ and $\log K_{\text{CuSA}_2}^{\text{CuSA}}$ are obtained from these curves by noting the values of pL at which $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5, respectively. For the 1 : 1 metal complex,

equation (6), and for 1 : 2 metal complex, equation (7) are used.

$$\log \bar{n}/(1 - \bar{n}) = \log K_{\text{CuSA}}^{\text{Cu}} - pL \quad (6)$$

$$\log \bar{n}/(2 - \bar{n}) = \log K_{\text{CuSA}_2}^{\text{Cu}} - pL \quad (7)$$

The values of $\bar{n}$ selected are between 0.2 and 0.8 for equation (6) and between 1.2 and 1.8 for equation (7). The value of $\log K_{\text{CuSA}}^{\text{Cu}}$ and $\log K_{\text{CuSA}_2}^{\text{Cu}}$, thus obtained are presented in Table 1. Our values are in good agreement with those in the literature¹⁵⁻²⁵.

Mixed ligand stability constant : From Fig. 1 it can be seen that Cu^{II} -8-hydroxyquinoline (1 : 1) curve (C) diverges from the 8-hydroxyquinoline curve (B) from pH 2.5 onwards from where 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -8-hydroxyquinoline complex formation starts and completes at pH 9.0. This indicates that 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -8-hydroxyquinoline complex also exists at higher pH. From the curve (F) it can also be seen that 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -salicylic acid complex formation starts at pH 6.0 and completes at pH 10.0. Since $\log K_{\text{CuOX}}^{\text{Cu}}$ is considerably greater than any one of

$\log K_{\text{CuSA}}^{\text{Cu}}$, Cu^{II} will be chelated by oxine in preference to any salicylic acid and so it is reasonable to assume that the predominated initial step in the mixed chelate formation must be the coordination of the salicylic acid by 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -8-hydroxyquinoline complex.

The equation used for the calculation of $\bar{n}$ (average number of salicylate anions associated with $[\text{Cu}(\text{OX})]^+$ is the same as in equation (5), where T_M is the concentration of $[\text{Cu}(\text{OX})]^+$ which is equal to the concentration of Cu^{II} used, and $\bar{n}_A$ is for second ligand H_2SA , $\bar{n}$ and pL values are calculated at different points in the pH range 4-9 and at $\bar{n}=0.5$ in the formation curve $pL = \log K_{\text{CuOXSA}}^{\text{CuOX}}$. More precise values are obtained by using equation (6). The average values thus obtained are presented in Table 1.

The data in Table 2 show that the order of stability for the mixed complex $\log K_{\text{CuOXSA}}^{\text{CuOX}}$ is salicylic acid (SA) > 5-choro (SA) > 3,5-dibromo (SA) < 3,5-diiodo (SA) > 3,5-dinitro (SA) < thio (SA).

The $\log K_{\text{CuOXSA}}^{\text{CuOX}}$ for all the salicylic acid (except in the case of Cu^{II} -8-hydroxyquinoline-3,5-dinitro (SA)) is slightly lower than $\log K_{\text{CuSA}}^{\text{Cu}}$ but considerably greater than $\log K_{\text{CuSA}_2}^{\text{Cu}}$. This suggests that the reaction of salicylic anion with 1 : 1 copper-salicylate is less favourable than with 8-hydroxyquinolinato-copper(II) cation. The very high value of $\log K_{\text{CuOX}}^{\text{CuOX}}$, than $\log K_{\text{CuOXSA}}^{\text{CuOX}}$ complexes can be best explained in terms of $d\pi \rightarrow p\pi$ back-donation between copper(II) and 8-hydroxyquinoline. 8-Hydroxyquinoline is a much better π acceptor than salicylic acids due to differences in bonding properties of heterocyclic nitrogen and carboxylato group. When 8-hydroxyquinoline is coordinated with copper(II), π electron transfer from the occupied copper(II) 'd' orbitals to unoccupied $p\pi$ orbitals of 8-hydroxyquinoline occurs reinforcing the σ electron transfer from ligand to metal. This kind of reinforcement takes place to a much smaller extent in the case of copper-salicylate complexes. This is further confirmed from the molecular orbital parameters calculated from our esr studies on these complexes²⁶. It can be inferred from the calculated molecular orbital parameters (Table 2) of all the ternary complexes that the in-plane π bonding parameter β^2 is weak compared to the σ bond parameter α^2 , whereas in the bis(8-hydroxyquinolinato) copper(II), β^2 is as strong as that of α^2 .

From the examination of the formation constants given in Table 1 the mixed complex formation takes place even though $\log K_{\text{CuOXSA}}^{\text{CuOX}}$ is lower than $\log K_{\text{CuOX}}^{\text{CuOX}}$. This can be explained on the basis of disproportionation concept given by Sigel²⁷, and

TABLE 2—MOLECULAR ORBITAL PARAMETERS, DISTRIBUTION DATA AND ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Molecular orbital parameters		log D	$\log K_{\text{CuHA}}^{\text{Cu}}$ + log D	Antifungal activity**			Antibacterial activity*		
		σ -bond α^2	in-plane π -bond β^2			a	b	c	d	e	f
1.	$\text{Cu}(\text{OX})_2$	0.748	0.824	1.99	14.00	18	12	12	6.2	12.5	25
2.	$\text{Cu}(\text{OX})(\text{SA})$	0.748	1	0.08	10.05	12	14	10	10	25	50
3.	$\text{Cu}(\text{OX})(\text{Cl-SA})$	0.798	0.865	0.41	10.02	12	14	10	10	25	50
4.	$\text{Cu}(\text{OX})(\text{Br-SA})$	0.721	0.967	0.58	9.88	12	14	10	10	25	50
5.	$\text{Cu}(\text{OX})(\text{I-SA})$	0.746	0.992	0.98	9.89	12	14	10	12	25	50
6.	$\text{Cu}(\text{OX})(\text{NO}_2\text{-SA})$	0.708	0.995	0.35	6.93	20	17	12	6.2	12.5	25
7.	$\text{Cu}(\text{OX})(\text{Thio-SA})$	0.765	0.980	0.04	9.15	10	12	9	12.5	35	75

* incubation period 24 h at 37°; in MIC ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)

** incubation period 48 h at 30°; average zone of inhibition in mm at 1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$

Fungi : a = *Aspergillus niger*,
Bacteria : d = *Staphylococcus albus*,

b = *Trichophyton rubrum*,
e = *Staphylococcus aureus*,

c = *Aspergillus fumigatus*,
f = *Shigella sonnei*.

the disproportionation reaction in the present system can be represented as

$$X = [\text{Cu}(\text{OX})(\text{SA})]^2 / [\text{Cu}(\text{OX})_2][\text{Cu}(\text{SA})_2] \quad (8)$$

$$\log X = \log \beta_{\text{CuOXSA}}^{\text{Cu}} - (\log \beta_{\text{CuOX}_2}^{\text{Cu}} + \log \beta_{\text{CuSA}_2}^{\text{Cu}}) \quad (9)$$

$$= \log K_{\text{CuOXSA}}^{\text{CuSA}} - \log K_{\text{CuOX}_2}^{\text{CuOX}} + (\log K_{\text{CuOXSA}}^{\text{CuOXSA}} - \log K_{\text{CuSA}_2}^{\text{CuSA}}) \quad (10)$$

For statistical reasons, the values expected²⁸⁻³⁰ for X (equation 8) is 4, i.e. $\log X = 0.6$ and the statistical value for one of the terms within brackets in equation (10) is 0.3 log units. Hence, under purely statistical conditions one would expect the ternary complex to be formed to the extent of 50% while the binary parent complexes should occur to the extent of 25% each.

Stability constant and antimicrobial activity : In these investigations it is found that, in general, the antimicrobial activity of 8-hydroxyquinoline (at concentrations 100 ppm for bacteria of 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$ for fungi) is intensified by 25 times or more, when it is chelated with Cu^{II} . The salicylic acid and the substituted salicylic acids and even their copper complexes possess very little activity against the growth of bacteria and fungi even at relatively very high concentrations (for bacteria even at > 500 ppm, for fungi > 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$) which may be due to their lower lipid solubility as indicated from their distribution data in between chloroform and 7.4 pH phosphate buffer (pH of biological model) which is considered as a good biological model to understand whether lipid soluble (Table 2). However, the ternary complexes of copper(II) with 8-hydroxyquinoline and salicylic acids are found to possess very effective toxic action against some organisms whereas in some cases, they have comparable activity as that of bis(8-hydroxyquinolato)copper(II) even though the former are less lipid soluble than the latter as indicated from their lipophilic tendency data.

Gerber and Block³⁴ have shown that 8-hydroxyquinoline is a strong inhibitor of cresolase (polyphenoloxidase) enzyme. This is a copper containing enzyme present in a wide variety of fungi. It is possible that within the cell copper of the chelate is transferred to another system with strong complexing power, such as thiols, porphyrine and 8-hydroxyquinoline remaining may combine with cresolase or other metal enzymes. It has been indicated³ that 1 : 2 chelate of Cu^{II} -8-hydroxyquinoline penetrates the cell and dissociates 1 : 1 half chelate and free 8-hydroxyquinoline. The 1 : 1 half chelate would then become the toxic entity by combining and blocking the metal substances on enzymes. Gershon and Parmesiani³⁵ supported the above mechanism and indicated that the antimicrobial activity of Cu^{II} -8-hydroxyquinolate is not due to the release of 8-hydroxyquinoline within the cell but due to the dissociated 1 : 1 complex such as that reported³.

The comparable activity of the mixed ligand complexes to that of bis(8-hydroxyquinolato)copper(II), even though the former possess less lipophilic character may be due to the dissociation of the mixed complexes at the site of action as shown below.

Both the 1 : 1 cationic complexes thus formed may be acting as toxic moieties at the site of action reinforcing the total activity. Thus in the mixed complexes in addition to 1 : 1 copperoxinate, 1 : 1 copper-salicylate may also be acting as a toxic agent which increases their activity. The 1 : 1 copper salicylate is better transported to the site of action as mixed complex than the bis(salicylato)copper(II) complexes which is found to possess very low activity most likely due to its higher hydrophilic character. The binary $\text{Cu}(\text{HSA})_2$ complexes individually show low activity due to their low lipid solubility which will not permit considerable amount of $\text{Cu}(\text{HSA})^+$ to go to the site of action.

If we examine the $\log K_{\text{CuSA}}^{\text{Cu}}$, $\log K_{\text{CuOXSA}}^{\text{CuOX}}$ and $\log D$ values of these complexes and their corresponding antimicrobial activity it appears that the antimicrobial activity is not dependent on either $\log K_{\text{CuOXSA}}^{\text{CuOX}}$ or $\log K_{\text{CuSA}}^{\text{Cu}}$ values. However, as can be seen from Table 2, except in the case of $\text{Cu}(\text{OX})(2\text{NO}_2 - \text{SA})$, that the complexes with the same value of $\log K_{\text{CuSA}}^{\text{Cu}} + \log D$, have equal toxic activity against many microorganisms. This further confirms the role of $\text{Cu}(\text{SA})^+$ in the mechanism of antimicrobial activity of the mixed complexes. The $\text{Cu}(\text{OX})(2\text{NO}_2 - \text{SA})$ has shown exceptionally high activity with all the organisms studied. These investigations further confirm that the chelation alone is not sufficient for enhancing the antimicrobial activity of a compound but it must be accompanied by lipid solubility also.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (R.Y.S. and R.P.R.) are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of research fellowships.

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